

DESCRIPTION OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF HERMENEUTIC COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: In the article, the factors affecting the development of hermeneutic competence of future music education teachers and their influence on the pedagogical process are thoroughly analyzed. Also, its necessity and pedagogical relevance today, priority tasks in preparing teachers for the process of hermeneutic competence development are highlighted.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, hermeneutic competence.

At the stage of development of today's education, the need to improve teaching methods, tools and forms of organization is increasing. Therefore, training specialists, in particular, creating educational-methodical and scientific literature suitable for the new era and applying them to the educational process, providing educational institutions with modern pedagogical communication tools, paying special attention to improving the quality of education necessary. In this regard, the development of a comprehensive and deep scientific-methodical foundation of modern music education remains one of the serious issues. The development of hermeneutic competence remains of special importance for a professional musician.

Educational standards are aimed not only at the process, but also at the results of education, at the formation of a self-satisfied specialist who is ready for professional activity, can adapt to society and benefit society. Competency issues A.V. Barannikov, E.A. Bystrova, V.A. Bolotov, V.P. Borisenkov, A. Dakhin, G.S. Zavatskaya, I.A. Zimnyaya, G.A. Larionova, O.E. Lebedev, A.F. Prisajnyaya, L.V. Savelyeva, G. Selevko, I.S. Sergeev, B.V. Serikov, M.A. Kholodnaya, A.V. . It was studied by such researchers as Khutorskoy, T.I. Shamova, N.M. Shansky.

In the process of preparing future music education teachers for the process of hermeneutic competence development, it is necessary to pay attention to the following as a priority:

1. The reflection factor (from the Latin *relatio* - message) is aimed at the development of certain situations acquired by students in the process of socialization of culture (at the level of education, profession, civic virtues, etc.) and entry into pedagogical activities.

2. The regulatory factor (lat. Regulare - regulation, direction) is aimed at developing specific standards of behavior and social control of the behavior and work of students in music.

3. The axiological factor (Greek axios - valuable) is related to the existence of a basic value system shared by all or most of its members in any social institution.

4. Integrative factor (lat. integer - whole) indicates that not only the successful operation of a particular social institution, but also the interests of the whole society should be prioritized for the goals and results of pedagogical activity.

5. The development factor is a type of "human institution" that not only provides pedagogical knowledge and skills, but also develops personality, prepares it for an independent creative life, real self-realization. At the stages of education, the main criteria of human development are intelligence and creative thinking, self-awareness and development, the concept of self-development is necessary, including the organization of emotional-volitional and motivational-need aspects.

6. Worldview factor - formation of a holistic worldview and attitude of students in accordance with modern achievements (fundamental sciences). Thus, the development of students' competence in music is carried out on the basis of the following directions:

motivation - students' understanding of the purpose and content of social pedagogical activity.

interest - increased interest of the student in the process of necessary activity and attitude in the social sphere of life and its effect.

acquisition - increasing students' theoretical and practical knowledge on the issues of developing hermeneutic competence.

self-control - learning to analyze results and compare them with expectations.

The need to develop the hermeneutic competence of music education teachers can be justified as follows:

First, it will be possible to form qualities of social activity based on the hermeneutic competence of music education teachers. Acquiring socially active qualities of a person is a complex pedagogical process, which combines universal, national, social, gender (male and female), sociotypical and individual development. The essence and nature of these differences, sexual consciousness

is formed only under the influence of communication with other people, socialization and education.

Secondly, based on the development of hermeneutic competence of music education teachers, it will be possible to adapt to education faster and achieve intellectual activity. Today, the main goal of organizing effective education based on the rapid adaptation of music teachers to education is to form the young generation into all-round mature, well-rounded people necessary for the development of our society. Adaptation (lat. adaptatio — adaptation) is the adaptation of the organism, for example, the sense organs, to the environmental conditions [3]. In other words, it is a feature of the formation of adequate relations of the organism with the external environment. A child does not have innate forms of behavior, and as he develops in the social environment, he learns three main components: territory (objects, means of their use), time (daily routine) and forms of behavior. So, from the moment a child is born, his activity is regulated within "child-adult" relations. In the case of school, in educational conditions, the school territory, educational activities and the new order adapt to the rules.

Therefore, on the basis of adapting students to education in music science, to organize education based on their initiative, independence, aimed at their thinking, focused on the development of independent thinking and consciousness, the result of which is formed as a product of personal activity, and in the future develops a well-rounded human personality, and increasing the effectiveness of education is expected.

Thirdly, it will be possible to ensure the effectiveness of the learning process based on the development of students' competence in music. Today, on the basis of the development of the continuous education system, many studies are being conducted aimed at increasing the cognitive activity, thinking, way of thinking and worldview of schoolchildren. Among them, significant work was carried out on the formation of the fundamentals of cognitive activity, mathematical thinking, speed of calculation, knowledge of the environment and the world, the way of thinking based on the worldview, reaction to events, and the conscious attitude of students at the educational stage [2]. . The results achieved in them are an important didactic basis for improving the thinking scope of students of junior school age, and through them, the formation of educational content is achieved based on modern requirements.

The teacher should not be indifferent to the students' interactions, conversations, and the need to interact. He should always find time to talk with

the class team and each student. Because, especially, students always clearly feel the teacher's attitude towards them, react sensitively. They will never share their thoughts and impressions with a teacher whose job is only to give assignments for daily homework. This harms the effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities conducted in the classroom.

Students should consider their teacher as a close friend, a confidant, a mentor who has the same interests as them, who can work and live harmoniously. Girls are especially sensitive to injustice. Cruelty and injustice towards girls leads to the appearance of negative qualities in their character. Therefore, one of the main conditions for character education in students is the clarity of requirements and confidence in the child's own strength and capabilities. It is especially dangerous for girls to lack confidence in themselves and their own strength, which usually occurs as a result of teachers and mothers saying to a girl that she is "a rag, a slob, she can't do anything." A music teacher should be able to find positive qualities in students and to skillfully use them, to skillfully stimulate the will power of students, to help them with advice and work in time, to know their own capabilities. should help in getting it.

Each new generation does not always create the basis of material and spiritual culture from scratch, but relies on existing cultural assets created by past generations. Historical succession is a necessary condition for the development of human society, including culture. Cultural assets are created at a certain stage of the society's development due to its needs and reflect the life of this society. There is no doubt that this legacy will serve as a means of ideological and emotional education that can provide significant mental and spiritual nourishment in shaping the spirituality of our youth, and will become a source of inspiration for all our artists. q is The formation of hermeneutic competence is not a one-time or even one-semester process, it should be continuous throughout the entire study at the university.

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